

A STUDY OF SELF-ESTEEM AND STUDY HABITS AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

***Dr. Nasreen Qusar**

Assistant Professor in Education,
BGSBU, Rajouri, J&K, India

ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: To find impact of Self- Esteem and Study Habits of secondary students.

Methodology: The sample was categorized on the basis of the obtained value of mean and standard deviation of study habits where, $M = \text{Mean}$ $\sigma = \text{Standard Deviation}$. Self Esteem Inventory By Dr. Stanley Coppersmiths and Study Habits Inventory By M.N. Palsane & Anuradha Sharma.

Findings: There are significant differences in self-esteem among secondary school students having high and low study habits. There are no significant sex differences in self esteem among secondary school students. There is no significant interaction between study habits and sex among secondary school students with self esteem as the dependent variable.

Key Words: Self Esteem, Study Habits. Intelligence, Students, Environment

INTRODUCTION

Self Esteem is a very complex concept that contributes to the uniqueness of human beings. It has been widely accepted that self-esteem or self-concept has an effect on many aspect of life including academic performance. Self-esteem may vary across different areas of experience and be dependent on sex, age and other defining roles. Either the individuals approve or disapprove of themselves just as one might approve or disapprove of some other object. The individuals will either respond favorably or unfavorably towards that object or event based from their standards, which may shape their self-esteem. In addition to self-esteem being linked to academic achievement (success with grades), academic confidence, or high self-esteem in academics has been found to have an even more significant relationship with academic achievement.

Some learners are better than other. It is an interesting question because there are differences in intelligence as well as study skill. Everyone vary in their study habits, some study in peaceful environment while others study listening to music, some study as they are forced to do so by their parents and others to build up their careers. Study habit is one of the factors which effect academic achievement. It is generally found that those students who have good study habit will surely achieve more than others who do not have good study habits.

It is well known fact that no two individual are alike in the World. They differ from each other. One individual is never like another in each and every respect. Even twins differ from each other in their tastes, intelligence and habits and this difference is there due to certain peculiar

traits found in every individual. These differences are due to the potent factors of heredity and environment.

Man among the living beings has the highest capacity to adopt new things and situations. Man is a social animal not only adopts to physical elements but also adjusts to habits in the society.

Muthian (1988) defines the standard of education in terms of integrated Personality Development. Self esteem is an important aspect of personality, a determinant of behavior and as such it leads the persons to behave in accordance with their own view of themselves. Self esteem is associated with personal satisfaction and effective functioning.

High level of self esteem is the key to success and achievement in the field of education. The concept of self esteem has become one of the most commonly and widely used psychological terms of the present. Firstly there is need to define the variables Self Esteem and Study Habits.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE:

1. To find significant differences in the self-esteem among secondary school students having high and low study habits.
2. To find significant sex differences in self-esteem among secondary school students.
3. To find significant interaction between study habits and sex with self esteem as the dependent variable among secondary school students.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pooja Bhagat (June 2016) . The study was conducted with the purpose to see the Relationship between Self- Esteem and Academic Achievement of Secondary school students. A sample consisted of 400 secondary school students of 9th class studying in government and private schools of Jammu District were taken for present study. **Khiliji(2014)**found that factors like self esteem and study habits impact on students performance Data collected from 10 government and 10 private schools in Rawalpindi. Out of 1100 hundred responded 600 hundred responses inducted in this study. The study show both factors influence students performance.**Cepeda (2013)** found that the study habits and self esteem of the students of the 10th year of General Basic Education at Provincia de Bolivar High School, are dependent on one another , that is, study habits and self esteem impact on students performance.**Mendoza (2011)** finds that the study habits of 52% of the students enrolled in 2nd year of Agronomy at Hermilio Valdizan University in Huanuca (UNHEVAL)are far appropriate, the academic performance being how, which also established the influence of the study habits on academic performance.**Margaret Zoller Booth and Jean M. Gerard (2009)** The investigates finds the relationship between self-esteem and academic achievement for young adolescents within two Western cultural contexts: the United States and England. Quantitative and qualitative data from 86 North American and 86 British adolescents were utilized to examine the links between self-esteem and academic achievement from the beginning to the end of their academic year during their 11th–12th year of age.

Anton and Angel (2004) conducted a study to analyze the relationship among study habits , self esteem and academic achievement. A total of 887 volunteer students from secondary schools both boys and girls. The study showed girls more socialized personality patterns than boys and having good study habits. **Suman Singh , Gunjan Bhatia and Jagadhri (2003)**. The present study was conducted to explore the relationship between self esteem and family environment. . A sample of 175 students was selected through random sampling and taken up for the study that the relationship between self esteem of school children and their family environment is positive and significant. Again there exists significant difference between the self esteem of students belonging to high and low family interaction group. The impact of socio economic status on the self esteem is found to be insignificant. It can be concluded that family interactions or environment influenced the self esteem of secondary school students.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

In the present study sample of the study was drawn employing stratified random sampling from private schools of Jammu district, the size of the sample was 250. The private schools from where certain number of boys and girls were randomly selected have been shown in the table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Details of institutions of students selected for Study.

S. No.	Name of the School	Boys	Girls	Total
1	Spring Blossoms Public High School, Bakshi Nagar, Jammu	14	11	25
2	Sri Guru Harkrishan Memorial High School, R.S. Pura, Jammu	12	13	25
3	St. Peter's High School, Jewel Chowk, Jammu	9	11	20
4	Shiksha Bhawan Hr. Sec. School, Bakshi Nagar, Jammu	13	12	25
5	Army Public School, Jammu	42	23	65
6	Army Public School, (Miran Sahib) Jammu	42	25	67
7	Shiksha Niketan Senior Sec. School, Jeevan Nagar, Jammu	11	12	23
	Total	143	107	250

Tool used:

Self Esteem Inventory

By Dr. Stanley Coopersmith

Study Habits Inventory

By M.N. Palsane & Anuradha Sharma

Data Analysis or Experimental Analysis:

After the data was collected by administering Self Esteem Inventory to each category two way analysis of variance (2x2) is used.

The mean differences in Self esteem with reference to Study habits in 2x2 factorial design are shown in the table:

Table 4.4 Summary of Two-Way Analysis of Variance (2x2 Factorial Design) for Self Esteem Scores.

Sources of Variance	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean square	F-ratio	Significance
Study Habits	1183.36	1	1183.36	6.92	Significant at 0.05 level
Sex	10.24	1	10.24	0.06	NS
Study Habits x Sex	125.44	1	125.44	0.73	NS
Within	16427.52	96	171.12		

Table 4.5 Combined Mean Values of Self Esteem Scores in different groups (with N=25) in each cell.

Group	High Study Habits	Low study Habits
Boys	65.76	56.24
Girls	62.88	58.24
Combined Mean	64.32	57.24

Research Findings

1. There are significant differences in self-esteem among secondary school student having high and low study habits.
2. There are no significant sex differences in self esteem among secondary school students.
3. There are no significant interaction between study habits and sex among secondary school students with self esteem as the dependent variable.

Conclusions

There are significant differences in self-esteem among secondary school students having high and low study habits. There are no significant sex differences in self esteem among secondary

school students. There are no significant interaction between study habits and sex among secondary school students with self esteem as the dependent variable.

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